

An updated checklist of the Serbian butterflies (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea Latreille, [1802]).

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Abstract

A new checklist of the butterflies of Serbia is presented, including both scientific and vernacular names. The differences between this and previous checklists are discussed, as well as current taxonomic issues. A new Red List is proposed, with supporting justification, and species considered regionally extinct (RE) are identified.

Key words

Butterflies — Checklist — Red List — Serbia.

Introduction

The Republic of Serbia, as a European country, is situated predominantly on the Balkan Peninsula, with a smaller portion extending into the Pannonian Plain. The total area of its territory covers 88,499 km² (Fig. 1).

The first comprehensive checklist of the butterflies of Serbia, then including Macedonia, was published by [Gradojević](#) (1930–31). That list contained 168 species, with a note that many of them had been recorded only in Macedonia. After a gap of 65 years, [Zečević](#) (1996) published a list referring solely to the territory of present-day Serbia, comprising 189 species. [Jakšić & Đurić](#) (2007) produced a new checklist enumerating 193 species. For the first time, vernacular names were presented systematically, following the principle of priority, while new vernacular names were proposed for species previously lacking them. Subsequent faunistic research revealed six additional species, incorporated into the revised list by [Jakšić et al.](#) (2013). [Popović & Verovnik](#) (2018) later published an updated checklist of the butterflies of Serbia, listing 199 species. Since then, several additional species have been confirmed for the Serbian fauna. Recently, a new *European Red List of Butterflies* ([van Swaay et al.](#) 2025) has been published, introducing revised categories of species threat levels. Considering that the *Red Data Book of Serbian Butterflies* ([Jakšić](#) 2003) appeared more than two decades ago, this moment offers an appropriate opportunity to present the current faunistic status of butterfly species in Serbia, along with their vernacular names and updated conservation categories.

Taxonomic and nomenclatural framework

The systematic order of families and lower taxa, as well as species nomenclature, follows [van Nieukerken et al.](#) (2011), [Dapporto et al.](#) (2022), [Taymans & Cuvelier](#) (2025a) and [Taymans & Cuvelier](#) (2025b).

The sequence and nomenclature adopted in the first publication was also followed by [van Swaay et al.](#) (2025).

The conservation status of species is likewise presented according to [van Swaay et al.](#) (2025):

RE - Regionally Extinct

EN - Endangered

VU - Vulnerable

NT - Near Threatened

LC - Least Concern

NA - Not Applicable.

Serbian vernacular names are based on [Jakšić & Đurić](#) (2007), [Jakšić et al.](#) (2013), and later publications concerning newly recorded species.

The results are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Republic of Serbia, Relief Map ([url](#)).

Table 1. Systematic list of Serbian butterflies with vernacular names and conservation status.

SCIENTIFIC NAMES	VERNACULAR NAMES	IUCN Red List Category (Serbia)	IUCN Red List Category (Europe)	IUCN Red List Category (EU27)
ORDER Lepidoptera Linnaeus, 1758				
SUBORDER Glossata Fabricius, 1775				
SUPERFAMILY Papilionoidea Latreille, [1802]	Дневни лептири			
FAMILY Papilionidae Latreille, [1802]	Једрилци			
SUBFAMILY Papilioninae Latreille, [1802]				
<i>Iphiclides podalirius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ветрило (Једрилац)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Papilio alexanor</i> Esper, [1800]	Соколов репак	NT	NT	NT
<i>Papilio machaon</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Ластин реп	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Parnassiinae Duponchel, [1835]				
<i>Driopa mnemosyne</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мнемозине	LC	LC	LC
<i>Parnassius apollo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Аполо	LC	LC	LC
<i>Zerynthia polyxena</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Ускршњи лептир	LC	LC	LC
<i>Allancastria cerisyi</i> (Godart, 1823)	Мирин лептир	LC	LC	LC

SCIENTIFIC NAMES	VERNACULAR NAMES	IUCN Red List Category (Serbia)	IUCN Red List Category (Europe)	IUCN Red List Category (EU27)
FAMILY Hesperidae Latreille, 1809	Скелари			
SUBFAMILY Heteropterinae Aurivillius, 1925				
<i>Heteropterus morpheus</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Карирани скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Carterocephalus palaemon</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Хеленина хесперида	NT	NT	VU
SUBFAMILY Hesperinae Latreille, 1809				
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i> (Esper, 1777)	Риђи скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hesperia comma</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ливадски скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Thymelicus acteon</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Травар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Thymelicus sylvestris</i> (Poda, 1761)	Сребрни скелар	VU	VU	VU
<i>Thymelicus lineola</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1808)	Смеђи скелар	VU	VU	VU
SUBFAMILY Pyrginae Burmeister, 1878				
<i>Spialia orbifer</i> (Hübner, [1823])	Дињицина хесперида	NT	NT	NT
<i>Spialia phlomidis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, [1845])	Сребрна хесперида	LC	LC	LC
<i>Favria cribellum</i> (Eversmann, 1841)	Мозаична хесперида	VU	VU	VU
<i>Muschampia floccifera</i> (Zeller, 1847)	Тотрљанов скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Muschampia orientalis</i> Reverdin, 1913	Оријентални скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Muschampia lavatherae</i> (Esper, [1783])	Чистац	NT	NT	NT
<i>Carcharodus alceae</i> (Esper, [1780])	Слезов скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erynnis tages</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Тамни скелар	LC	LC	NT
<i>Pyrgus malvae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Слезова хесперида	NT	NT	NT
<i>Pyrgus carthami</i> (Hübner, [1813])	Рибар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus sidae</i> (Esper, [1784])	Липицина хесперида	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus andromedae</i> (Wallengren, 1853)	Алпијска хесперида	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus serratulae</i> (Rambur, [1839])	Загасити зујавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus armoricanus</i> (Oberthür, 1910)	Зујавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus alveus</i> (Hübner, [1803])	Проседа хесперида	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus cinarae</i> (Rambur, [1839])	Пиргавац пешчаник	LC	LC	LC
FAMILY Pieridae Duponchel, [1835]	Белци			
SUBFAMILY Dismorphiinae Schatz, 1886				
<i>Leptidea duponcheli</i> (Staudinger, 1871)	Балкански белац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Leptidea morsei</i> (Fenton, 1882)	Фрушкогорски белац	RE	VU	Vu
<i>Leptidea juvernica</i> Williams, 1946	Загасити белац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Leptidea sinapis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Горушичин белац	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Coliadinae Swainson, 1827				
<i>Gonepteryx rhamni</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Жутац (Лимуновац)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias hyale</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Златни поштар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias alfacariensis</i> Ribbe, 1905	Златна осмица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias erate</i> (Esper, [1805])	Степски поштар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias croceus</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	Шафрановац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias myrmidone</i> (Esper, [1781])	Зановетак	RE	VU	EN
<i>Colias caucasica</i> Staudinger, 1871	Кавкаски поштар	VU	VU	VU

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SUBFAMILY Pierinae Duponchel, [1835]					
	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Глоговњак (Глоговац)	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pontia edusa</i> (Fabricius, 1777)	Зелени купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris brassicae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris rapae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мали купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris mannii</i> (Mayer, 1851)	Далматински купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris ergane</i> (Geyer, [1828])	Планински купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris napi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Жиличасти купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris balcana</i> Lorković, [1969]	Балкански купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Euchloe ausonia</i> (Hübner, [1804])	Чипкасти белац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Зорица	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Anthocharis gruneri</i> Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]	Мала зорица	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Anthocharis damone</i> Boisduval, 1836	Пештерска зорица	EN	EN	EN
FAMILY Riodinidae Grote, 1895		Пегавци			
SUBFAMILY Nemeobiinae Bates, 1868					
	<i>Hamearis lucina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Смеђи пегавац	LC	LC	LC
FAMILY Lycaenidae [Leach], 1815		Плавци			
SUBFAMILY Lycaeninae [Leach], 1815					
	<i>Lycaena helle</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Љубичасти дукат	NT	NT	NT
	<i>Lycaena thersamon</i> (Esper, [1784])	Пегави дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena dispar</i> ([Haworth], 1802)	Велики дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena hippothoe</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Долински дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena candens</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, [1844])	Балкански дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena virgaureae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena tityrus</i> (Poda, 1761)	Бакренац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena alciphron</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Кисељаков дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena phlaeas</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Ватрени дукат	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Theclinae Swainson, 1831					
	<i>Thecla betulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Брезов дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Favonius quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Храстов репка	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Callophrys rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Купинов репка	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Satyrium pruni</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Трњинар	VU	VU	VU
	<i>Satyrium ilicis</i> (Esper, [1779])	Храстовчић	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Satyrium w-album</i> (Knoch, 1782)	Шумски репка	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Satyrium spini</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Трњинин репка	VU	VU	VU
	<i>Satyrium acaciae</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	Мали репка	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Polyommatae Swainson, 1827					
	<i>Leptotes pirthous</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Краткорепи селац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lampides boeticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Дугорепи селац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Cacyreus marshalli</i> Butler, 1898	Мушкатлин плавац	NA	NA	NA
	<i>Celastrina argiolus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Крковин плавац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Tarucus balkanica</i> (Freyer, [1843])	Драчац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Phengaris alcon</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Мали пегавац	NT	NT	NT

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<i>Phengaris arion</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики пегавац	NT	NT	NT
<i>Phengaris teleius</i> (Bergsträsser, 1779)	Мочварни пегавац	VU	VU	VU
<i>Pseudophilotes vicrama</i> (Moore, 1865)	Душицин плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Scolitantides orion</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Жедњаков плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Iolana iolas</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1816)	Пуцавац	NT	NT	NT
<i>Glaucopsyche alexis</i> (Poda, 1761)	Зеленотрби плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cupido argiades</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Краткорепи плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cupido decolorata</i> (Staudinger, 1886)	Бледи плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cupido alcatas</i> (Hoffma[n]nsegg, 1804)	Ливадски плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cupido osiris</i> (Meigen, [1829])	Озирисов плавац	LC	LC	NT
<i>Cupido minimus</i> (Fuessly, 1775)	Малени плавац	NT	NT	NT
<i>Plebejus argus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Стооки плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Plebejus idas</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Идин плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i> (Bergsträsser, 1779)	Блистави плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aricia artaxerxes</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Тамносмеђи плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aricia agestis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Чапљинац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aricia anteros</i> (Freyer, 1839)	Алпијски плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Kretania sephirus</i> (Frivaldszky, 1835)	Зефиоров плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Eumedonia eumedon</i> (Esper, [1780])	Здравчев плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Византијски плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Agriades optilete</i> (Knoch, 1781)	Боровничар	VU	VU	VU
<i>Lysandra bellargus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Потковичар	NT	NT	NT
<i>Lysandra coridon</i> (Poda, 1761)	Сребрнкасти плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Гладишев плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus eros</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1808)	Планински плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus thersites</i> (Cantener, 1835)	Вучарица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus daphnis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Крзави плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus amandus</i> (Schneider, 1792)	Граоричар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus dorylas</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Тиркизни плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus damon</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Дамон	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus admetus</i> (Esper, [1783])	Смеђан	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus ripartii</i> (Freyer, 1830)	Планински смеђан	NT	NT	NT
FAMILY Nymphalidae Swainson, 1827	Шаренци			
SUBFAMILY Limenitidinae Behr, 1864				
<i>Neptis sappho</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Грахоровац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Neptis rivularis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Медуниковац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Limenitis reducta</i> Staudinger, 1901	Козолистовац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Limenitis populi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики тополњак	LC	LC	NT
<i>Limenitis camilla</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)	Мали трепетљикар	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Heliconiinae Swainson, 1827				
<i>Issoria lathonia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мала седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Brenthis hecate</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Белоглавичар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Brenthis ino</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Инова седефица	LC	LC	LC

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<i>Brenthis daphne</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Карирана седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Argynnis paphia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Госпођак	LC	LC	LC
<i>Argynnis pandora</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Пандорина седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Speyeria aglaja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велика седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Fabriciana niobe</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ниобина седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Fabriciana adippe</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Љубичина седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria eunomia</i> (Esper, [1800])	Старопланинска седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria graeca</i> (Staudinger, 1870)	Грчка седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria pales</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Планинска седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria selene</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Бисерна седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria euphrosyne</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Пролећна седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria dia</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Ткачева седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria titania</i> (Esper, [1793])	Титанија	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Apaturinae Boisduval, 1840				
<i>Apatura iris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Таласњак	LC	LC	LC
<i>Apatura metis</i> Freyer, 1829	Панонски преливац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Apatura ilia</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Мали преливац	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Nymphalinae Swainson, 1827				
<i>Araschnia levana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Шумска риђа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Vanessa cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Стричковац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Vanessa atalanta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Адмирал (Лепотић)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aglais io</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Паунац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Копривар	NT	NT	NT
<i>Polygonia egea</i> (Cramer, [1775])	Војишничар	RE	LC	LC
<i>Polygonia c-album</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Риђа седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Nymphalis vau-album</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Мрки многобојац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Nymphalis polychloros</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики копривар (Многобојац)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Nymphalis xanthomelas</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Жутоноги многобојац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Nymphalis antiopa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мртвачки плашт	LC	LC	NT
<i>Euphydryas aurinia</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Мочварни шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Euphydryas maturna</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Жути шаренац	VU	VU	VU
<i>Melitaea trivia</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Дивизмин шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea didyma</i> (Esper, [1778])	Црвени шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea arduinna</i> (Esper, [1783])	Фрејеров шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea phoebe</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Различков шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea ornata</i> Christoph, 1893	Кристофов шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea cinxia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Обични шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea diamina</i> (Lang, 1789)	Мрки шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea athalia</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Боквичин шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea aurelia</i> Nickerl, 1850	Златни шаренац	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Satyrinae Boisduval, [1833]				
<i>Kirinia roxelana</i> (Cramer, 1777)	Шумски решеткар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Kirinia climene</i> (Esper, [1783])	Тимочки решеткар	LC	LC	LC

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<i>Lopinga achine</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Драганин окаш	EN	NT	NT
<i>Pararge aegeria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Шумски пегавец	LC	LC	LC
<i>Lasiommata maera</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики окаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Lasiommata petropolitana</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	Планински окаш	LC	LC	NT
<i>Lasiommata megera</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Зидни окаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мали сатир (Мала ценонимфа)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha rhodopensis</i> (Elwes, 1900)	Родопска ценонимфа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha glycerion</i> (Borkhausen, 1788)	Кестењаста ценонимфа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha leander</i> (Esper, [1784])	Ливадска ценонимфа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha orientalis</i> Rebel, [1909]	Илирска ценонимфа	NT	NT	NT
<i>Coenonympha arcania</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Бисерна ценонимфа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia ottomana</i> Herrich-Schäffer, [1847]	Турска еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia cassioides</i> (Hochenwarth, 1792)	Планинска еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia oeme</i> (Hübner, [1804])	Маслиничар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia gorge</i> (Hübner, [1804])	Загасита еребија	LC	LC	NT
<i>Erebia pandrose</i> (Borkhausen, 1788)	Снежна еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia euryale</i> (Esper, [1805])	Мала еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia ligea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велика еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia rhodopensis</i> Nicholl, 1900	Родопска еребија	NT	NT	NT
<i>Erebia alberganus</i> (Prunner, 1798)	Старопланинска еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia medusa</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Пролећна еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia aethiops</i> (Esper, 1777)	Окаста еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia orientalis</i> Elwes, 1900	Самотна еребија	NT	NT	NT
<i>Erebia epiphron</i> (Knoch, 1783)	Обична еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia pronoe</i> (Esper, [1780])	Црноруба еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia melas</i> (Herbst, 1796)	Црна еребија	NT	NT	NT
<i>Hyponephele lycaon</i> (Kühn, 1774)	Ливадски смеђаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hyponephele lupinus</i> (Costa, 1836)	Вуков смеђаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Окасти смеђаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyronia tithonus</i> (Linnaeus, 1771)	Вратар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Maniola jurtina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Воловско око	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melanargia larissa</i> (Geyer, [1828])	Балканска шах-табла	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melanargia galathea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Шах-табла	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia syriaca</i> (Staudinger, 1871)	Источна хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia fagi</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Шумска хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia semele</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia volgensis</i> (Mazochin-Porshnyakov, 1952)	Балканска хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia statilinus</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	Јесења хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Minois dryas</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Модрооки сатир	LC	LC	LC
<i>Brintesia circe</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Шумски вратар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Arethusana arethusa</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Јесењи ливадар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Satyrus ferula</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Велики сатир	LC	LC	LC
<i>Chazara briseis</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)	Самотњак	LC	LC	LC

Discussion and conclusions

The occurrence of the taxon *Kretania pylaon* (Fischer, 1832) in Serbia remains a matter of debate. Kudrna *et al.* (2015) provided aggregated distribution data for the *K. pylaon* complex, whereas Popović & Verovnik (2018) listed only the species *Kretania sephirus* (Frivaldszky, 1835). The first concrete evidence that these are distinct species, *Kretania pylaon brethertoni* Brown 1976, and *K. sephirus*, was provided by Coutsis & De Prins (2006), who demonstrated a difference in haploid chromosome number (*K. pylaon brethertoni* Greece $n = 37$; *K. sephirus* Bulgaria $n = 19$). The current consensus recognises them as two separate species (Dapporto *et al.* 2022; Taymans & Cuvelier 2025a; van Swaay *et al.* 2025). Taxonomically, the *Kretania pylaon* species-group complex (= *K. pylaon* complex) comprises five European species: *K. pylaon*, *K. sephirus*, *Kretania trappi* (Verity, 1927), *Kretania hespericus* (Rambur, [1839]), and *Kretania brethertoni* (Brown, 1976), whose species status is subject to debate. Balint & Fiedler (1992) recorded *K. sephirus* from Flamunda (Deliblato, Banat Province, Serbia), describing its habitat as calcareous, sandy, or loess-dominated steppe. The larvae of both species feed on plants of the genus *Astragalus*, of which 17 species occur in Serbia (Diklić 1972). Approximately 30 published studies (Jakšić 2022) deal with *K. sephirus* in Serbia; however, none provide substantiated evidence for the presence of *K. pylaon* in the country. Further cytotaxonomic research and DNA barcoding of specimens from Serbian territory could help clarify this unresolved issue.

According to Dincă *et al.* (2021), Case 14 of shared barcodes, further taxonomical research may be needed.

Lorković (1953; 1954) described *Erebia cassioides illyromacedonica* on the Macedonian side of Mt. Šar Planina as a distinct subspecies, compared to *Erebia cassioides illyrica* from Mt. Durmitor in Montenegro. We have found this subspecies at several sites (Mt. Šar Planina: Ljuboten, Piribreg, Vrbeštički jalovarnik) on the Serbian side of Mt. Šar Planina (Fig. 2).

Lopinga achine (Scopoli, 1763) was, until now, known only from a literature record in the vicinity of Majdanpek ("Univerzitetska domena" - Majdanpek District, Eastern Serbia) and, the entire collection, including this specimen, was destroyed during the Second World War (Živojinović, 1950). Remarkably, in June of this year, Mihajlo Vujić and Ivan Tot discovered a population of this species in western Srem, Vojvodina ([url](#)).

Fig. 2. *Erebia cassioides illyromacedonica*. Above: ♂ underside. Serbia, Mt. Šar Planina, Ljuboten, 2300–2490 m, 24.viii.1994. Leg. P. Jakšić. Below: ♀ underside. Serbia, Mt. Šar Planina, Piribreg, Vrbeštički Jalovarnik, 1700 m, 3–4.viii.1987, Leg. P. Jakšić.

Fig. 3. *Erebia manto* ♂ genitalia. Montenegro, Čakor, 1800 m, 18.viii.1988., Gen. slide no. 1393, Leg. P. Jakšić.

Fig. 4. *Polygonia egea* ♂ underside. Serbia, Priština, Mt. Grmija, 700 m, 1.viii.1971. Leg. P. Jakšić.

What can be expected in the future?

In their monograph devoted to the Macedonian side of Mt. Šar Planina, Krpač *et al.* (2021) list two species occurring near the border with Serbia: *Muschampia alta* (Schwingenschuss, 1942) from Vratnica and *Agriades pyrenaica dardanus* (Freyer, [1843]) without precise locality data. The authors themselves did not record these species but referred to earlier publications. Unfortunately, no field research has been conducted on the Serbian side of the Mt. Šar Planina to confirm their presence.

A similar situation applies to the species *Erebia manto* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) (Fig. 3). It was confirmed in Montenegro at the site Čakor, 1800 m (Jakšić & Pešić 1995). The borderline between Montenegro and Kosovo and Metohija in that sector follows the line Starac (2426 m) - Čakor (1849 m) - Planinica (1963 m). Future fieldwork will almost certainly show that this species also occurs on the Serbian side of Mt. Čakor.

An important issue concerns species known from earlier records but not observed in the past fifty years. Two species belong to this group:

Leptidea morsei (Fenton, 1882), was only known from Mt. Fruška Gora. Specimens are preserved in the collections of Lorković (1930–1931) and the industrialist-collector Miloš Rogulja from Novi Sad (Jakšić 1993). Both records originate from Mt. Fruška Gora. The species has not been found there for the past ninety years.

Colias myrmidone (Esper, [1781]), was last recorded from Eastern Serbia: Sokolovica, Bor, and Mt. Stol, dating to 1970 (Zečević & Radovanović 1974). The species has not been observed in Serbia in the past fifty years.

These two species may therefore be regarded as regionally extinct (RE).

Another group includes species occasionally recorded beyond the limits of their natural range:

Papilio alexanor Esper, [1800], was recently recorded in western Serbia at Mt. Zlatibor, Čajetina, village Stublo (Vukajlović *et al.* 2025). The nearest known locality is Gacko in eastern Bosnia and Herzegovina (Lelo 2008), approximately 100 km in a straight line from Čajetina.

Cacyreus marshalli Butler, 1898, was discovered in the city of Niš, represented by a single specimen (Milojković *et al.* 2021).

Polygonia aegae (Cramer, [1775]), was collected by Jakšić on 1.viii.1971 at Mt. Grmija, near Priština (Fig. 4). During three decades of research on Mt. Grmija (1969–1999), this was the only specimen found. The larval host plant, *Parietaria officinalis*, is absent from that locality (Krivošej 2013). The species was later observed near Niš, in the Jelašnička Klisura Gorge (Đurić, Popović & Verovnik 2010). These three species appear to exhibit range fluctuations in response to ongoing climatic changes. As early as 1994, Ocokolić convincingly demonstrated the cyclical alternation of wet and dry periods in Serbia, and the observed range shifts correspond to these climatic oscillations.

Based on the results presented (Table 1), a total of 201 butterfly species have been recorded in the territory of Serbia. Compared with the previous checklist (Popović & Verovnik 2018), the fauna of Serbia has been enriched by three newly recorded species: *P. alexanor*: W Serbia, Stublo village, Čajetina (Vukajlović *et al.* 2025), *Tarucus balkanica* (Freyer, [1843]): SE Serbia, Pčinja Valley, Čivčije locality (Tot *et al.* 2022) and *C. marshalli*: Serbia, Niš, Palilula City Park (Milojković *et al.* 2021).

In conclusion, faunal richness is a dynamic category: over the past century, some species previously present in Serbia have disappeared, while others, until recently unknown, have been newly recorded in its territory. The conservation status of species is presented according to the categories applied in Europe, excluding the 27 EU member states (van Swaay *et al.*, 2025). The categories proposed in that publication were adopted, except for *L. morsei* and *C. myrmidone*, which are here classified as regionally extinct species (RE).

Author contribution

Predrag Jakšić: conceptualization, field work, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

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